

CHEMICAL SCIENCES

PHYSICO-CHEMICAL INVESTIGATION OF PHASE EQUILIBRIUM IN NON-QUASI-BINARY e_1 - e_2 SECTION OF QUASI-TERNARY SYSTEM $PbGa_2S_4$ - Ga_2S_3 - $YbGa_4S_7$

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Abstract

Using physicochemical methods of analysis: differential-thermal analysis (DTA), X-ray diffraction (XRD), microstructure (MSA), determination of density and microhardness, the phase equilibrium in the section $e_1(PbGa_2S_4)_{0.60}(Ga_2S_3)_{0.40}$ - $e_2(YbGa_2S_4)_{0.85}(Ga_2S_3)_{0.15}$ of the quasi-ternary system $PbGa_2S_4$ - Ga_2S_3 - $YbGa_4S_7$ was studied and the T-x phase diagram of the section was constructed. To determine the location of the ternary eutectic $PbGa_2S_4$ - Ga_2S_3 - $YbGa_4S_7$ in the quasi-ternary system, the section e_1 - e_2 was studied. It was found that the section e_1 - e_2 is a non-quasi-binary section of the quasi-ternary system $PbGa_2S_4$ - Ga_2S_3 - $YbGa_4S_7$. The projection of the liquidus surface of the quasi-ternary system $PbGa_2S_4$ - Ga_2S_3 - $YbGa_4S_7$ is constructed and the coordinates of its mono- and non-variant equilibrium are indicated.

Keywords: system, phase equilibrium, non-quasi-binary, diagram, density

Introduction

The components of the quasi-ternary system $PbGa_2S_4$ - Ga_2S_3 - $YbGa_4S_7$ are semiconductors with unique properties. Let us consider each of these components separately. The physical properties of the $PbGa_2S_4$ compound have not been sufficiently studied. The phonon spectrum of the $PbGa_2S_4$ crystal was studied by the authors of [1] using Raman scattering. The photoelectric properties of the $PbGa_2S_4$ compound were studied by the authors of [2,3]. The $PbGa_2Se_4$ compound, which belongs to this family, is photosensitive in a wide spectral region (400-1200 μ m). In previously published works [2,3], the following were studied in $PbGa_2Se_4$ crystals: photoconductivity (PC) spectra at various applied electric fields, temperature quenching of the photocurrent (TCP), PC kinetics, etc.

The Ga_2S_3 compound and new phases based on it have photoelectric [4,5] and luminescent [6-8] properties and are semiconductors used as energy converters.

The $YbGa_2S_4$ compound and new phases obtained from it are materials with luminescent and magnetic properties. Luminescent materials suitable for use as phosphors [9-12] were obtained by treating the $YbGa_2S_4$ compound with ions of various rare earth elements. In [10], the luminescent properties of a compound containing $YbGa_2S_4$:5 % Er^{+3} were studied. The aim of the work is to determine the coordinate of the ternary eutectic by means of a physicochemical study of the phase equilibrium in the non-quasi-binary section $e_1(PbGa_2S_4)_{0.60}(Ga_2S_3)_{0.40}$ - $e_2(YbGa_2S_4)_{0.85}(Ga_2S_3)_{0.15}$ of the quasi-ternary system $PbGa_2S_4$ - Ga_2S_3 - $YbGa_4S_7$.

Experimental part

Alloys in section $e_1(PbGa_2S_4)_{0.60}(Ga_2S_3)_{0.40}$ - $e_2(YbGa_2S_4)_{0.85}(Ga_2S_3)_{0.15}$ of the quasi-ternary system $PbGa_2S_4$ - Ga_2S_3 - $YbGa_4S_7$ were synthesized from compounds $PbGa_2S_4$, $YbGa_4S_7$ and Ga_2S_3 in quartz ampoules with air pumped out to a pressure of 0.133 Pa in the temperature range of 900-1100°C. Then, alloys in section e_1 - e_2 from compositions $e_1(PbGa_2S_4)_{0.60}(Ga_2S_3)_{0.40}$ - $e_2(YbGa_2S_4)_{0.85}(Ga_2S_3)_{0.15}$ in a wide range of concentrations were synthesized by the ampoule method. To obtain alloys of the e_1 - e_2 section in an equilibrium state, they were subjected to heat treatment at a temperature of 600°C for 240 hours.

Differential-thermal analysis of the samples was carried out on a THERMOSCAN-2 pyrometer. Al_2O_3 was used as a standard, the heating rate was 5°C/min. X-ray phase analysis was carried out on a D2 PHASER X-ray diffractometer. A $CuK\alpha$ cathode and a Ni filter were used as an irradiator. Microhardness was calculated using a PMT-3 metallographic microhardness tester. Microhardness is determined by pressing a tetrahedral pyramid with an angle of 136° into the surface of the sample under a load of 0.15-0.20 N. Microstructural analysis was carried out on a MIM-8 microscope. The density of the samples was determined by the pycnometric method, using toluene as a filler.

Discussion of results

After achieving the full composition of the initial components $(PbGa_2S_4)_{0.60}(Ga_2S_3)_{0.40}$ and $(YbGa_2S_4)_{0.85}(Ga_2S_3)_{0.15}$ in a wide range of concentrations, the alloys of the e_1 - e_2 section were synthesized by the ampoule method. The alloys of the system are

resistant to air, water and organic solvents. They dissolve well in strong mineral acids (HNO₃, H₂SO₄). After completing the homogenization of the samples, the physicochemical analysis of the alloys of the e₁-e₂ section was carried out.

The results of differential-thermal analysis of the alloys of section e₁-e₂ show that three endothermic effects are observed in the thermograms of the alloys of the system. The presence of multiple thermal effects in the system indicates the presence of multiple phases, which means that complex interactions occur between the components. After heat treatment, microstructural

analysis of the alloys of the section was carried out and it was found that there are two- and three-phase regions in the system. Figure 1 shows the microstructure of alloys with 10, 30 and 70 mol. % (YbGa₂S₄)_{0.85}(Ga₂S₃)_{0.15} sections e₁ (PbGa₂S₄)_{0.60}(Ga₂S₃)_{0.40} - e₂ (YbGa₂S₄)_{0.85}(Ga₂S₃)_{0.15}. As can be seen from Figure 1, alloys with a concentration of 10 and 70 mol. % (YbGa₂S₄)_{0.85}(Ga₂S₃)_{0.15} belong to the two-phase region, and the alloy with a concentration of 30 mol. % (YbGa₂S₄)_{0.85}(Ga₂S₃)_{0.15} belongs to the three-phase region.

Fig. 1. Microstructure of the alloys of section e₁ (PbGa₂S₄)_{0.60}(Ga₂S₃)_{0.40} - e₂ (YbGa₂S₄)_{0.85}(Ga₂S₃)_{0.15}. 1-10, 2-30, 3-70 mol % (YbGa₂S₄)_{0.85}(Ga₂S₃)_{0.15}.

X-ray phase analysis of the alloys of section e₁ (PbGa₂S₄)_{0.60}(Ga₂S₃)_{0.40} - e₂ (YbGa₂S₄)_{0.85}(Ga₂S₃)_{0.15}

shows that there are many mixed lines in the diffraction patterns of the alloys.

Fig. 2. T-x phase diagram of the e₁ (PbGa₂S₄)_{0.60}(Ga₂S₃)_{0.40} - e₂ (YbGa₂S₄)_{0.85}(Ga₂S₃)_{0.15} system.

Based on the results of physico-chemical analysis methods, the T-x phase diagram of section e₁-e₂ was constructed (Fig. 2). The phase diagram of the section is non-quasi-binary. For clarity of the phase diagram of the section e₁-e₂, Figure 3 shows a projection of the liquidus surface of the quasi-ternary system PbGa₂S₄-

Ga₂S₃-YbGa₄S₇. As can be seen from Figure 3, the section e₁-e₂ passes through two- and three-phase fields, passing through the quasi-ternary system PbGa₂S₄-Ga₂S₃-YbGa₄S₇.

Fig. 3. Projection of the liquidus surface of the quasi-ternary system $PbGa_2S_4-Ga_2S_3-YbGa_4S_7$.
1- $PbGa_2S_4$, 2- Ga_2S_3 , 5- $YbGa_4S_7$.

The liquidus surface of the quasi-ternary system $PbGa_2S_4-Ga_2S_3-YbGa_4S_7$ consists of the crystallization region of the compounds $PbGa_2S_4$, Ga_2S_3 and $YbGa_4S_7$.

In the solid triangle $PbGa_2S_4-Ga_2S_3-YbGa_4S_7$, binary eutectics e_2 , e_3 , e_4 and one ternary eutectic equilibrium E are observed. At the point of the ternary eutectic E, the equilibrium $M \leftrightarrow PbGa_2S_4 + Ga_2S_3 + YbGa_4S_7$ is achieved, the temperature of which is 640°C.

The crystallization region of the $PbGa_2S_4$ compound is surrounded by the equilibrium curves e_3E , Ee_4 . The crystallization region of the Ga_2S_3 compound is surrounded by the equilibrium curves e_3E and Ee_2 . The $YbGa_4S_7$ compound is surrounded by the monovariant equilibrium curves e_2E , Ee_4 .

In the concentration range of 0-100 mol. % below the liquidus line there are two-phase regions of the composition (L + Ga_2S_3). The composition of the ternary eutectic (E) in the system is 30 mol. % ($YbGa_2S_4$)_{0.85}(Ga_2S_3)_{0.15}, and the temperature is 640°C. At the ternary eutectic point there is a four-phase equilibrium $M \leftrightarrow Ga_2S_3 + PbGa_2S_4 + YbGa_4S_7$. In the concentration range of 0-30 mol. % ($YbGa_2S_4$)_{0.85}(Ga_2S_3)_{0.15} below the liquidus curve there is a three-phase region L + Ga_2S_3 + $PbGa_2S_4$. A more three-phase region L + Ga_2S_3 + $YbGa_4S_7$ is observed in the concentration range of 30-100 mol. % ($YbGa_2S_4$)_{0.85}(Ga_2S_3)_{0.15}. Table 1 shows some physical and chemical properties of alloys of the section e_1 ($PbGa_2S_4$)_{0.60}(Ga_2S_3)_{0.40} - e_2 ($YbGa_2S_4$)_{0.85}(Ga_2S_3)_{0.15}.

Table 1.

Composition, DTA results, microhardness and density measurements of alloys of section e_1 ($PbGa_2S_4$)_{0.60}(Ga_2S_3)_{0.40} - e_2 ($YbGa_2S_4$)_{0.85}(Ga_2S_3)_{0.15}

Composition, mol %		Thermal effects, °C	Density, q/cm ³	Microhardness, MPa		
e_1	e_2			$PbGa_2S_4$	Ga_2S_3	$YbGa_2S_4$
100	0,0	980	4,90	2100	-	-
95	5,0	775,845,1000	4,90	2120	-	-
90	10	720,830,1010	4,88	2140	-	-
80	20	640,720,1020	4,86	2140	930	-
70	30	640,1030	4,85	2140	900	-
60	40	640,525,1030	4,82	2140	900	2250
50	50	670,790,1025	4,79	-	900	2250
40	60	710,840,1015	4,66	-	900	2250
30	70	765,840,1010	4,75	-	900	2250
20	80	825,930,1000	4,73	-	-	2250
10	90	900,980	4,72	-	-	2250
0,0	100	960	4,70	-	-	2250

Conclusion

In order to clarify the coordinate of the triple eutectic point of the quasi-ternary system $\text{PbGa}_2\text{S}_4\text{-Ga}_2\text{S}_3\text{-YbGa}_4\text{S}_7$, the internal section $e_1(\text{PbGa}_2\text{S}_4)_{0.60}(\text{Ga}_2\text{S}_3)_{0.40}$ - $e_2(\text{YbGa}_2\text{S}_4)_{0.85}(\text{Ga}_2\text{S}_3)_{0.15}$ was studied using physico-chemical methods of analysis: (DTA, X-ray diffraction, MSA, as well as determination of microhardness and density). It was found that the section $e_1 - e_2$ of the quasi-ternary system $\text{PbGa}_2\text{S}_4\text{-Ga}_2\text{S}_3\text{-YbGa}_4\text{S}_7$ is non-quasi-binary. The region of the solid solution was not determined based on the initial components. The projection of the liquidus surface of the quasi-ternary system $\text{PbGa}_2\text{S}_4\text{-Ga}_2\text{S}_3\text{-YbGa}_4\text{S}_7$ was constructed and the coordinates of its mono- and invariant equilibria were indicated.

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